

NANOCOMPOSITES BASED ON NONWOVEN BORON NITRIDE NANOTUBE SHEETS: PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the development of nanocomposites based on impregnation of boron nitride nanotube (BNNT) buckypaper. A low viscosity aerospace-grade epoxy (Araldite MY0510) is used for the impregnation of buckypaper sheets containing about 20 vol% BNNT. Characterization results based on scanning electron microscopy, dynamic mechanical analysis and tensile testing are presented. The results suggest that nearly full impregnation of BNNT buckypaper was achieved, which was associated with significant enhancement of resin mechanical properties. A Young's modulus and ultimate tensile strength of 7.7 GPa and 40 MPa, respectively, were obtained for the BNNT nanocomposites. The developed nanocomposite behaves as a brittle material (i.e., strain at failure of <1%), while the optical transparency along with potentially unique thermal and mechanical properties make the material interesting for many applications including in the aerospace and defense sectors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Boron nitride nanotubes (BNNTs) have excellent mechanical properties, a wide energy band gap, high thermal conductivity and superb resistance to oxidation [1, 2]. These characteristics make BNNTs attractive nanofillers for the fabrication of mechanically and thermally enhanced lightweight composites for a wide range of aerospace and defence applications. The fabrication of BNNT-polymer composites via dispersion/mixing of BNNTs into bulk polymers has been recently reported including aramid and polyester [3], polymethyl methacrylate [4], polycarbonate [5] and epoxy resins [6] among other matrices [7] and these composites have shown improvement in thermal and mechanical properties versus neat resin. However, the number of studies of BNNT composites is vastly smaller than for carbon nanotube (CNT) composites and, in contrast to CNTs, nonwoven nanotube sheets (commonly called buckypaper) have not been available for BNNTs. In fact, a significant challenge in development of BNNT-based papers and composites has been the unavailability of large quantities of BNNTs. Recently, benefiting from the development of a unique technology to make pilot-scale quantities of BNNTs (>20 g/hr) at the National Research Council Canada (NRC) [8, 9], several parallel studies on the development of BNNT-based macroscopic assemblies, their chemical functionalization and fabrication of BNNT composite materials have been initiated by the authors. This includes a new report [10], summarized here, describing BNNT-epoxy composites prepared for the first time by epoxy-impregnation of free-standing BNNT buckypapers.

BNNT-based buckypaper composites have several potential advantages versus CNT composites. First, BNNT is thermally more stable than CNT, particularly in an oxygen environment. Also, the

development of transparent or semi-transparent composites is possible by using BNNT buckypaper or BNNT thin films. This work focuses on the development and characterization of resin-impregnated BNNT buckypaper composites. Over the past decade, there have been many studies on the development of nanocomposites based on CNT buckypaper and many different polymers and processing techniques have been employed, to varying level of success [11-14]. The main advantages of buckypaper-based nanocomposites over other nanocomposite manufacturing techniques (e.g., direct resin and CNT mixing) are the possibility of manufacturing composites that contain a high content of CNTs and the preferential alignment of CNT (“2D” random in plane or “1D” aligned sheets [14]). In fact, the content of CNT in buckypaper composites often reaches 20-30 vol%, compared with <5.0% vol (and often <1% vol) that can be achieved by direct mixing techniques.

2 LARGE-SCALE BNNT PRODUCTION

The accessibility of multi-gram-scale and larger samples of high-quality, small-diameter BNNT reached a critical point over the last two years. In particular, two large-scale, continuous methods based on plasma torch technology have been reported [9,15] and a commercial product based on a laser method is now available [16]. Our approach at NRC employs a radio frequency plasma torch to vaporize hexagonal boron nitride (hBN), although other sources of B and N can be used. The product from a single, continuous synthesis batch run is shown in Fig. 1. The features of the plasma, including high temperature ($\sim 10^4$ K), abundance of radicals, and high cooling rate allow for realization of a high yield of small diameter BNNTs, which had previously proved difficult. This new method, called the hydrogen-assisted BNNT synthesis (HABS) method, makes use of hydrogen to achieve high yield by impeding re-formation of N_2 . In the HABS approach, the presence of hydrogen leads to formation of B-N-H containing intermediate species, which provide a source of available nitrogen for BNNT growth that is much more reactive than the direct $N_2 + B$ reaction, as explained in more detail elsewhere [9].

Figure 1: Images of as-produced BNNT material at various length scales. Reproduced from [9] with permission

3 MATERIALS

A commercial tridentate epoxy resin used in the aerospace industry, triglycidyl p-aminophenol (TGAP; trade name: Araldite MY0510), was used as the polymeric matrix precursor. Aradur HT 976, 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS), was chosen as the curing agent. This resin exhibits a glass transition temperature, room temperature viscosity and room temperature density of 275°C, 550-850 mPa.s and $\rho=1.2$ g/cm³, respectively. Both the epoxy resin and curing agent were used as-received.

In order to fabricate BNNT buckypaper, a mixture of BNNT/solvent was vacuum-filtered through a polycarbonate membrane (20 μ m pore size) using a home-built vacuum table that accommodates rectangular sheet moulds up to 30 cm \times 30 cm in size [9,10]. In this case, an 8 cm \times 20 cm mould was used. After filtration, the buckypaper was sandwiched between sheets of parchment and compressed.

After drying at room temperature under compression, the buckypaper peeled easily from the filtration membrane and was further dried by baking at 100°C for 2 h.

Impregnation of small pieces of BNNT buckypaper (3.5 cm × 5.0 cm; ~60 μm thick) was performed using capillary forces [10]. A hot-plate was used to heat the buckypaper to approximately 100°C. The epoxy resin, pre-heated to 100°C, was poured on top of the BNNT buckypaper. The change in color of buckypaper from white to light yellow (resin color) suggested the impregnation of buckypaper sheets was complete after less than a minute. Excess resin on both surfaces of the buckypaper sheet was wiped off using lint-free absorbent wipes. The sample was then placed between two glass plates coated with a release agent. A small weight (5 kg) was placed on top of the glass plates to apply light pressure and avoid any warpage of the BNNT nanocomposite during cure. The specimen was cured in a convection oven according to the curing protocol provided by the resin manufacturer (120°C for 2 hours, immediately postcuring at 177°C for two hours). An image of impregnated buckypaper is shown in Figure 2, demonstrating that a measure of optical transparency of BNNT buckypaper is maintained after resin impregnation.

Figure 2. A 60 μm thick BNNT buckypaper impregnated by epoxy resin.

4 CHARACTERIZATION

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM): SEM images were taken with a Hitachi High Technologies S-4800v.

Rheology: A TA instruments AR2000 Rheometer with an Environmental Test Chamber (ETC) accessory was used to measure the viscosity of the MY0510 epoxy resin and hardener as a function of time at four different temperatures (60, 100, 120, and 140°C).

Tensile tests: The mechanical properties of the nanocomposite thin films were determined by testing free-standing rectangular specimens under tension until failure. A micro-tensile test frame (Fullam Substage Test Frame) was used to measure the Young's modulus (E), ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and ultimate tensile strain (ϵ_{\max}) of the pristine BNNT buckypaper and BNNT nanocomposite films. At least five strips of each material were tested using a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the viscosity of MY0510 epoxy as a function of time at four different temperatures (60, 100, 120 and 140°C). The viscosity at room temperature was roughly 10 Pa.s, decreasing to about 0.1 Pa.s at 100°C. A temperature of 100°C was considered optimal for the infiltration process as it provided a sufficiently low viscosity that was relatively constant over a period of over three hours, which is much longer than the timescale of the infiltration process (see Materials section).

Figure 4 shows SEM images of a resin-impregnated BNNT composite at four different magnifications (5,000×, 20,000×, 40,000× and 60,000×) taken from the cross sectional area of a fractured specimen. A comparison between SEM images of pristine and impregnated BNNT

buckypaper (Figures 1 and 4) suggests a different morphology, indicative of successful infiltration of resin into the BNNT buckypaper. Note that at low magnification (Figure 4a), it is clear that there is a thin layer of neat resin ($\sim 3\text{-}4\ \mu\text{m}$) on the surface of the composite due to incomplete removal of excess resin. From this image, it is also clear that impregnation is rather uniform over the cross sectional area of the BNNT buckypaper composite. As seen in Figure 4b, impregnation is not perfectly complete and there are small voids. Higher-magnification SEM images (Figure 4c-d) suggest that pull-out of BNNT ropes occurs on the fractured surface of the BNNT composites. The long loose fibers on the surface of the specimen suggest an energy absorbing mechanism before failure. This phenomenon can also be seen in CNT buckypaper composites [11]. A good interaction (i.e., wetting of BNNT with resin) can also be observed in the higher magnification images. The alignment of BNNT ropes in Figure 4d can be attributed to sample preparation for SEM imaging.

Figure 3. Viscosity of the MY0510 epoxy system as a function of time for 4 different temperatures

Figure 4. SEM images taken from a cross-section of a resin-impregnated BNNT buckypaper at four different magnifications: (a) 5,000 \times , (b) 20,000 \times , (c) 40,000 \times and (d) 60,000 \times .

Table 1 reports the typical physical properties of BNNT buckypaper before and after impregnation. Weight and dimensions of buckypaper before and after impregnation were used to obtain the density and void content of pristine BNNT buckypaper and its resin-impregnated composite. For void content estimation, densities of 1.9 and 1.2 g/cm³ were assumed for BNNTs and the epoxy, respectively. A BNNT volume fraction of 20% (i.e., 80% void) was obtained for the pristine buckypaper, which is close to values often obtained for CNT buckypaper sheets [10]. After impregnation, a void content of ~5% was estimated for the fabricated BNNT composite, suggesting the effectiveness of the impregnation technique. These results were in agreement with microscopy results, presented in Figure 4.

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties of pristine and epoxy-impregnated BNNT buckypaper sheets

	Density (g/cm ³)	Void Content (%)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Strain at Failure (%)
Pristine BNNT BP	0.43	80%	0.37	2	0.8
BNNT BP/epoxy	1.34	5%	7.7	42	0.6

Note: According to the resin manufacturer, a Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength and strain failure of 3.5 GPa, 71 MPa and 2.7%, respectively, are reported for the bulk resin.

For pristine BNNT buckypaper, the Young's modulus was 0.37 GPa and the ultimate tensile strength was ~2 MPa. The strain at failure of 0.8% for BNNT buckypaper, however, is lower than a typical CNT buckypaper, which is often >1.5%. After impregnation, the Young's modulus of BNNT buckypaper was improved by almost 20 times (7.7 GPa) as compared to the pristine BNNT buckypaper (0.37 GPa) and 2 times as compared to the neat epoxy. The ultimate tensile strength of BNNT composite (42 MPa) showed a 20 times enhancement versus the pristine BNNT buckypaper. However, this value is still only about 60% that of the neat epoxy (~71 MPa). Measured strain at failure of 0.6% indicates the brittleness of the composite. A stronger interaction between BNNT and epoxy, for example by using functionalization, can possibly result in the development of BNNT buckypaper composites with better mechanical properties and is the subject of ongoing studies.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study focused on development of buckypaper nanocomposites containing about 20 vol% BNNTs. A low viscosity, aerospace-grade epoxy (Araldite MY0510) was used for impregnation of buckypaper sheets. Density measurements suggest that almost full impregnation of BNNT buckypaper was achieved, as supported by SEM images. The impregnation resulted in significant enhancement of mechanical properties. A Young's modulus and an ultimate tensile strength of 7.7 GPa and 42 MPa were respectively obtained for resin-impregnated BNNT composites (an enhancement of 20× as compared to the pristine BNNT buckypaper for both properties). The optical transparency of the developed nanocomposite is interesting for many applications in aerospace and defense, while the research should be directed to address the brittleness of the present BNNT buckypaper composites.

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